

Coordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum

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The coordination chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum has been the subject of immense interest in recent times due to its role in certain biological systems. The complex salts of the anion $(\text{MoOX}_5)^{-}$ (where $X = \text{Cl}$ or Br) may be prepared by the reduction of molybdenum trioxide in concentrated halogen acid (HX) either electrolytically¹⁻² or chemically²⁻³ followed by the addition of the appropriate halide (RX). James and Wardlaw¹ thus isolated and studied pyridine, quinoline and trimethyl ammonium salts.

In our investigations molybdenum trioxide was reduced with hydriodic acid in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid. To the green solution thus obtained the hydrochloride of the corresponding nitrogen base organic compound was added in calculated amount. The solution on concentration and subsequent cooling gave crystals of the desired compound. In some cases the precipitation was initiated by passing hydrogen chloride gas. The compounds were purified by recrystallisation from concentrated hydrochloric acid.

Analysis: Molybdenum was estimated⁴ after decomposing the compound with sodium peroxide and subsequent precipitation of the sulphide from alkaline thiomolybdate with dilute sulphuric acid. Ignition of the precipitate of molybdenum sulphide gave MoO_3 . Chloride was estimated in the filtrate and washings as silver chloride. Nitrogen was estimated by microanalytical methods.

The oxidation number of the molybdenum was determined by ceric sulphate method and it was found to be 5.0 in these salts. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out in Guoy balance of field-strength 8500 gauss. The values are recorded here as, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.830 (X_M T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M. where X_M = molar susceptibility after diamagnetic correction and T is the absolute temperature. The properties and analytical results of these compounds are recorded in Table I.

These salts are extremely sensitive to moisture; they turn brown and ultimately blue. With water and alcohol they give reddish-brown solutions which again turn green when hydrogen chloride gas is passed through it. From the results of magnetic susceptibility measurements it appears that these salts correspond to one unpaired spin as expected for quinquevalent molybdenum. Detailed investigations of these salts both in solution and in

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3. J. P. Simon and P. Souchay, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1956, 1402.
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the solid state are in progress which will be published later on. Except these, hydroxylamine, hydrazine and triethanolamine compounds also have been isolated but unlike others these salts are very unstable and hence could not be obtained in a pure state by usual procedure.

TABLE I

Compound	Color		Mo (%)	Cl (%)	N (%)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
2:2'-dipyridyl-oxopentachloromolybdate (V). $C_{10}H_{10}N_2MoOCl_5$	Green	<i>Found</i>	21.12	39.08	6.24	1.73
		<i>Calc.</i>	21.46	39.64	6.26	
1:10-phenanthroline-oxopentachloromolybdate (V). $C_{12}H_{10}N_2MoOCl_5$	Yellowish	<i>Found</i>	19.60	36.82	5.09	1.72
	Green	<i>Calc.</i>	20.96	37.61	5.94	
Ethylenediamine-oxopentachloromolybdate (V). $C_8H_{10}N_2MoOCl_5$	Deep Green	<i>Found</i>	25.98	50.49	8.32	1.65
		<i>Calc.</i>	27.32	50.47	7.98	
8-oxyquinoline-oxopentachloromolybdate (V). $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_2MoOCl_5$	Green	<i>Found</i>	16.10	29.63	4.32	1.60
		<i>Calc.</i>	16.51	30.49	4.81	
Aniline oxopentachloromolybdate (V). $C_{12}H_{12}N_2MoOCl_5$	Yellowish	<i>Found</i>	20.61	37.87	6.25	1.79
	Green	<i>Calc.</i>	20.11	37.15	5.87	

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